

MOLDAVIAN AND ROMANIAN FEMININE PERSONAL NAMES WITH LATIN ORIGIN, CANONIZED BY THE ORTHODOX CHURCH

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Abstract

The research object of the present text is Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names Latin by origin, canonized by the Orthodox Church. The observation is implemented on the corpus of twenty-four anthroponyms, feminine by gender, and their variants.

Every one of those twenty-four Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names is derived from another personal name and that is why they are classified according to the main characteristics of the anthroponym, used as a basis during the process of derivation, i. e. if it is masculine or feminine by gender, if it is Latin or Moldavian/Romanian by origin.

Keywords: Moldavian/Romanian feminine personal name, Latin origin, canonized.

The research object of the present text are Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names Latin by origin, canonized by the Orthodox Church.

The observation is implemented on the corpus of twenty-four anthroponyms, feminine by gender, and their variants. As a main source of information are used "Dicționar onomastic românesc" ("Romanian Dictionary of Onomastics") by N. A. Constantinescu and the sites www.kurufin.ru and www.behindthename.com. All additional sources of information, used in order the research, presented in that text, to be complete, are presented at the very end, in *References*, and are cited in the footnotes.

Every one of those twenty-four Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names is derived from another personal name and that is why they are classified according to the main characteristics of the anthroponym, used as a basis during the process of derivation, i. e. if it is masculine or feminine by gender, if it is Latin or Moldavian/Romanian by origin:

- (1) Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names derived from a Roman feminine name:
 - *Agripina* (*Agrăpina*, *Agripina*, *Agripină*, *Agripina*¹) < *Agrippina* < *Agrippinus* (Roman cognomen, derived from the Roman personal name *Agrippa*, used also as a cognomen)²;
 - *Diana*³ < *Diana* (the name of the Roman goddess of the moon, hunting, woods and birth-giving, the Roman equivalent of the Greek goddess *Artemis*; meaning unknown⁴);
 - *Lucia* (*Lucica*)⁵ < *Lucia* < *Lucius*⁶ (Roman personal name, derived from the Latin noun *lux, lucis, f* - "light")⁷;
 - *Natalia* (*Natalița*⁸, *Nătălița*⁹)¹⁰ (< *Natalia* (Medieval Latin name, derived from the Latin *Natale Domini* - "Christmas Day"¹¹, from (*dies*) *Natalis* - "Birthday; connected with the birth-giving"¹², or from *natalis, e* - "of birth, natal"¹³));

- *Petronela*¹⁴ (< *Petronilla* (a diminutive of the Roman feminine name *Petronia*¹⁵) < *Petronius* (Roman family name, derived probably from the Latin noun *petro*, *petronis*, *m* – “yokel¹⁶; old ram¹⁷” or from the Greek *πέτρα* (*ἕλι.*)/*πέτρος* – “stone; rock¹⁸”));
- *Tatiana*¹⁹ (< *Tatiana* < *Tatianus* (Roman cognomen, derived probably from the name of the legendary Sabine king *Titus Tatius*²⁰ or from the Greek verb *τάσσω* – “affirm”²¹).

(2) Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names derived from a Moldavian/Romanian masculine personal name, Latin by origin:

- *Antonina* (< *Antonin* < *Antoninus*²² (Roman family name, used also as a cognomen, derived from the Roman family name *Antonius*)²³);
- *Claudia*²⁴ (< *Claudiu* < *Claudius* (Roman family name, derived from the Latin adjective *claudus* (lame²⁵) or from *claudius* (locked²⁶);
- *Dominica* (*Dominica*²⁷, *Domnița*, *Dumnica*, *Dumnița*²⁸) (< *Dominic* < *Dominicus* (Medieval Latin, derived from the Latin adjective *dominicus* (the Lord’s, possessed by God²⁹) or from the Latin *dominica*, *ae, f* (Sunday³⁰, mistress³¹));
- *Emilia* (*Emilica*) (< *Emil* (*Emilică*) < *Aemilius* (Roman family name, derived from the Latin noun *aemulus*, *i, m* (enemy)³²);
- *Flaviana* (< *Flavian* < *Flavianus* (Roman family name, derived from the Latin adjective *flavus* (yellow, golden³³) or from another Roman family name *Flavius*)³⁴);
- *Iulia* (*Iulica*) (< *Iuliu* (*Iulică*) < *Iulius/Julius*³⁵ (Roman family name, derived from the Greek adjective *ἰοῦλος* (curly, hairy³⁶) or from the name of the Roman god *Iuppiter/Jupiter*³⁷);
- *Iustina* (*Iiustina*³⁸) (< *Iustin* < *Iustinus/Justinus* (Roman cognomen, derived from another Roman cognomen *Iustus/Justus*)³⁹);
- *Marcela* (< *Marcel* < *Marcellus* (Roman cognomen, used in *gens Claudia*, derived from the Roman personal name *Marcus*⁴⁰ or from the Latin noun *marcellus*, *i, m* (little hummer⁴¹);
- *Mariana* (< *Marian* < *Marianus* (Roman cognomen, derived from the Roman family name *Marius*)⁴²);
- *Marina* (*Marena*, *Marenca*, *Marinca*, *Mărena*, *Mărenca*, *Mărina*, *Mărină*, *Mărinca*, *Mărincea*, *Măronca*⁴³) (< *Marin* (*Marinel*, *Marinică*) (< *Marinus*⁴⁴, a Roman cognomen, derived from the Latin adjective *marinus* (sea,

possessed by the sea⁴⁵) or from the Roman family name *Marius*⁴⁶) or directly from the feminine form (i. e. *marina*) of the Latin adjective *marinus* (sea, possessed by the sea⁴⁷);

- *Martina*⁴⁸ (< *Martin* < *Martinus* (Roman cognomen, derived from the form for Gen. sg. *Martis* of the name of the Roman god of war *Mars*)⁴⁹);
- *Paula* (*Paulica*) (< *Paul* (*Pavel*, *Pavelică*, *Păvălaș*, *Pava*, *Pavu*, *Paulica*) < *Paullus*/*Paulus* (Roman personal name, used also as a cognomen in *gens Aemilia*, derived from the Latin adjective *paulus* (little, modest)⁵⁰);
- *Sabina* (*Sabinuța*)⁵¹ < *Sabin* < *Sabinus*, a Roman cognomen, used in *gens Calvisia* and *gens Claudia*, derived from the Latin word *Sabinus* (Sabine, a member of a tribe of the Sabines⁵²), from the Greek word *Σάββα* (Saturday) or from a Hebrew word meaning *an old man*⁵³;
- *Valentina* (*Ualentina*)⁵⁴ < *Valentin* < *Valentinus*, a Roman cognomen, derived from another Roman cognomen *Valens*⁵⁵ or directly from the Latin *valentines* (the one, who is healthy, sound⁵⁶) or directly from the feminine form (i. e. *valentina*) of the Latin *valentines* (the one, who is healthy, sound⁵⁷);
- *Valeria*⁵⁸ < *Valeriu* < *Valerius* (a Roman family name, derived from the Latin verb *valeo* (to be strong, to be healthy⁵⁹) or from the Latin present participle *valens*, *valentis* (strong, healthy⁶⁰)).

(3) Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names derived from a Moldavian/Romanian feminine personal name Latin by origin:

- *Cristina* (*Christina*, *Hristina*) < *Cristiana* (*Christiana*) < *Cristian* or *Christian* (a Moldavian/Romanian masculine personal name Latin by origin) < *Christianus* (a Medieval Latin name, derived from the Latin noun *christianus*, *i, m* (christian)⁶¹).

(4) Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names derived directly from a Roman masculine name:

(4.1.) a family name:

- *Cecilia* (*Cecilica*)⁶² < *Caecilius*, derived from the Latin adjective *caecus* (blind⁶³) or from the Latin verb *cado* (fall⁶⁴);

(4.2.) a Medieval Latin name:

- *Laura* (*Laurica*) < *Laurus* < *laurus*, *i, f* (laurel)⁶⁵.

The biggest is the group of the Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names that are derived from Moldavian and Romanian masculine personal names, Latin by origin (15). The less is the number of the observed feminine anthroponyms, derived from another Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal name – only one example (*Cristina* < *Cristiana*).

Number of the names, derived from a masculine name (17), is bigger than that of the names, derived from another feminine anthroponym (7).

Sixteen of the observed names in the present research are derived from another Moldavian or Romanian name, while only eight are derived directly from a Roman name (six from a feminine Roman name and two from a masculine one).

All the Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names with Latin origin, observed in the present text, are canonized by the both Churches, i. e. the Orthodox and the Catholic one.

Notes

¹Constantinescu, 1963.

²Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; www.kurufin.ru; www.leksykony.interia.pl

³The name became popular during the Renaissance (see www.behindthename.com).

⁴It is possible the name to be derived from pre-Indo-European word **deivos* – “god” (www.kurufin.ru), from an Indo-European root meaning “heavenly, divine” (Voinov *et alii*, 1990; www.behindthename.com), from the Latin *deus, i, m* – “god” (Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*; Knappová, 1986), from the feminine form (i. e. *diviana*) of the Latin *divianus* – “the one, who is divine” (Kovachev, 1995) or from the Latin *dies, diei, m/f* – “day” (<http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologicky-slovník-mien>).

⁵The saint is a patron of merchants, glaziers, and writers; and of the Italian towns *Perugia* and *Syracuse* as well (www.kurufin.ru). She is also a protector of the blind people because the saint herself was blind (www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru).

⁶Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Kol *et alii*, 2011; www.kurufin.ru; www.leksykony.interia.pl

⁷Knappová, 1986; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru; www.leksykony.interia.pl; <http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologicky-slovník-mien>

⁸Constantinescu, 1963.

⁹www.kurufin.ru.

¹⁰According to the Orthodox tradition the saint is a patron of the happy marriage (www.kurufin.ru).

¹¹Doichinovich, 2010; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru; <http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologicky-slovník-mien>

¹²Constantinescu, 1963; Garkovich, 1966; Kol *et alii*, 2011; www.ksiegaimion.com; www.leksykony.interia.pl; <http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologicky-slovník-mien>

¹³Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Ilchev, 1959; Knappová, 1986; Kol *et alii*, 2011; Kovachev, 1995.

¹⁴The saint is a protector of the people, travelling through the woods. In the French court she is thought to be the patron of the Dauphin. People believe that she helps high temperature and fever to be healed (www.kurufin.ru). It is believed that she is a daughter of St. Peter (Ilchev, 1959; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru).

¹⁵Ilchev, 1959; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

¹⁶Knappová, 1986; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

¹⁷Doichinovich, 2010; Dvoretzky, 1976; Knappová, 1986; Kol *et alii*, 2011; Kovachev, 1995; Voinov *et alii*, 1990.

¹⁸Knappová, 1986; Kol *et alii*, 2011; www.leksykony.interia.pl; <http://slovník.dovrecka.sk/etymologicky-slovník-mien>.

¹⁹In Russia the saint is believed to be the protector of all students because the decision for the creation of The Moscow University (the first university in Russia) is taken by the Empress Elisabeth on the 12th of January, 1755, or the day celebrated as St. Tatiana's day (www.kurufin.ru).

²⁰Ilchev, 1959; Petrovsky, 1955; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

²¹www.kurufin.ru.

²²Constantinescu, 1963.

²³Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Knappová, 1986; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

²⁴The name became popular after the 16th c. Before that it is rarely used (www.behindthename.com).

²⁵Constantinescu, 1963; Doichinovich, 2010; Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Ilchev, 1959; Knappová, 1986; Kol *et alii*, 2011; Petrovsky, 1955; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru; www.leksykony.interia.pl; <http://slovník.dovrecka.sk/etymologicky-slovník-mien>.

²⁶Kovachev, 1995.

²⁷www.kurufin.ru.

²⁸Constantinescu, 1963.

²⁹Constantinescu, 1963; Kovachev, 1995; www.behindthename.com; www.dzietki.org; www.kurufin.ru; www.leksykony.interia.pl; <http://slovník.dovrecka.sk/etymologicky-slovník-mien>.

³⁰Ilchev, 1959.

³¹Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Petrovsky, 1955; www.ksiegaimion.com.

³²Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Kol *et alii*, 2011; Petrovsky, 1955; www.behindthename.com; www.ksiegaimion.com; www.kurufin.ru; www.leksykony.interia.pl; <http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologický-slovník-mien>.

³³www.kurufin.ru.

³⁴Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Petrovsky, 1955; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru; <http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologický-slovník-mien>.

³⁵Constantinescu, 1963.

³⁶Batakliiev, 1979; Kol *et alii*, 2011; Kovachev, 1995; www.behindthename.com, www.kurufin.ru.

³⁷www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

³⁸Constantinescu, 1963.

³⁹Constantinescu, 1963; Doichinovich, 2010; Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Ilchev, 1959; Knappová, 1986; Kol *et alii*, 2011; Petrovsky, 1955; www.kurufin.ru.

⁴⁰Voinov *et alii*, 1990; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru; <http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologický-slovník-mien>.

⁴¹Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Knappová, 1986; Petrovsky, 1955.

⁴²Constantinescu, 1963; Ilchev, 1959; Knappová, 1986; Kovachev, 1995; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

⁴³Constantinescu, 1963.

⁴⁴*ibidem*.

⁴⁵Knappová, 1986; Kol *et alii*, 2011; Kovachev, 1995; Petrovsky, 1955; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

⁴⁶*ibidem*.

⁴⁷Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Ilchev, 1959; Kol *et alii*, 2011; Kovachev, 1995; <http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologický-slovník-mien>.

⁴⁸The saint is one of the patrons of Rome (www.behindthename.com).

⁴⁹Constantinescu, 1963; Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Ilchev, 1959; Knappová, 1986; Kol *et alii*, 2011; Kovachev, 1995; www.behindthename.com; www.ksiegaimion.com; www.kurufin.ru; <http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologický-slovník-mien>.

⁵⁰Constantinescu, 1963; Doichinovich, 2010; Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Knappová, 1986; Kol *et alii*, 2011; Kovachev, 1995; www.behindthename.com;

www.ksiegaimion.com; www.kurufun.ru; www.leksykony.interia.pl;
http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologický-slovník-mien.

⁵¹The saint is a patron of housewives (www.kurufin.ru).

⁵²Kovachev, 1995; Petrovsky, 1955; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

⁵³Ilchev, 1959.

⁵⁴Constantinescu, 1963.

⁵⁵Constantinescu, 1963; Doichinovich, 2010; Ilchev, 1959; Knappová, 1986; Kol *et alii*, 2011; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru;
http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologický-slovník-mien.

⁵⁶Kovachev, 1995.

⁵⁷*ibidem*.

⁵⁸The saint is a patron of Tibodo town (Luisiana, U.S.A.) (www.kurufin.ru).

⁵⁹Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Ilchev, 1959; Kovachev, 1995; Voinov *et alii*, 1990; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

⁶⁰http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologický-slovník-mien.

⁶¹Collins, 1997; Knappová, 1986; Kovachev, 1995; Petrovsky, 1955; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru;
http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologický-slovník-mien.

⁶²The saint is a patron of music, musicians, composers, singers and poets; and also of the French town Alby and The National Music Academy “Santa Cecilia” in Rome (www.kurufin.ru).

⁶³Knappová, 1986; Kovachev, 1995; Petrovsky, 1955; Voinov *et alii*, 1990; www.behindthename.com; www.ksiegaimion.com; www.kurufun.ru; www.leksykony.interia.pl; http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologický-slovník-mien.

⁶⁴Kovachev, 1995.

⁶⁵Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Ilchev, 1959; Kovachev, 1995; Petrovsky, 1955; www.behindthename.com; www.ksiegaimion.com; www.kurufun.ru; http://slovník.dovrečka.sk/etymologický-slovník-mien.

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